

Implementation of Learning Management Training Program at PT LPK Jamiatul Indonesia Edutech Certification in Improving Work Quality

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Implementation, Management, Training Programs, PT.LPKJIEC, Quality of Work

Received : 5 April

Revised : 19 April

Accepted : 22 May

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ABSTRACT

The job training program organized by LPK JIEC is a program that aims to improve the competence of the workforce in Blitar in particular and throughout Indonesia. LPK JIEC is committed that the participants in this job training program can start their own business which includes planning, implementing, coaching, and evaluating learning. The purpose of this study was to determine the implementation of the job training program and the factors that hindered the successful implementation of the job training program at JIEC LPK. The method in this study uses a qualitative descriptive method. Data collection techniques used are interviews, observation, and documentation. The data validity technique uses source, method, and theory triangulation. Data analysis techniques include data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions. The theoretical concept used in this study is Edward III's theory, namely 1) communication, 2) resources, 3) disposition, and 4) bureaucratic structure. The results of this study indicate that the implementation of job training programs in Blitar district is not optimal, especially in terms of communication and resources. In its implementation there are still obstacles such as 1) a shortage of instructors, 2) the absence of a Vocational Training Center, and 3) budget constraints in implementing job training programs. Evaluation of learning outcomes is carried out periodically, participants are satisfied with the training activities provided by PT. LPK JIEC to gain knowledge and skills.

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is a vast country. So is the population. The total population of Indonesia is ± 276.362 million. To get life skills education, many methods can be used, one of which is through a job training institute (LPK). According to Septyana, Job Training Institutions are a form of non-formal education unit organized for people who need the provision of knowledge, skills, life skills, and attitudes to develop themselves, develop their profession, work, be independent businesses, and/or continue their education to a higher level. LPK provides a variety of life skills such as language skills, skills in operating computer applications, sewing skills and many more. One of the Non-Formal educational or individual legal entity that meets the requirements to organize job training.

As a direct consequence of the ongoing process of regional autonomy, there has been healthy competition between these regions to develop their respective regions by mobilizing human resources in these regions. Thus there are higher regional and national job market opportunities, because the need for a reliable and ready-to-use workforce has become a basic need for a region so that the region can develop. Thus, the implementation of tourism development policies cannot only rely on 4 (four) main indicators as stated by Edward, namely communication, bureaucracy, disposition and institutions.

Appropriate indicators to measure the successful implementation of the job training program at the Blitar district manpower office would follow Edward III's view. According to Edward III, policy implementation needs to be done because there are policy or program issues that need to be resolved and overcome. According to Mulyadi, four indicators are formulated as sources of problems as well as preconditions for the success of the implementation process, namely communication, resources, dispositions, and bureaucratic structure. Because the four indicators are interrelated, it is necessary to integrate synergistically and intensively to achieve program implementation performance., as well as the four signs above directly affect program implementation and work at the same time and interact with each other to help and hinder program implementation obstacles. Or indirectly, these signs affect program implementation through the impact of each of these signs. Researchers use these signs to measure the successful implementation of job training programs based on expert opinion, namely George Edward III, which is related to the phenomena that occur, namely: First, there is a lack of public awareness of job training objectives and programs. Second, Blitar Regency has large companies but the lack of job training with companies has made the implementation of job training programs in Blitar Regency not optimal. Third, the problem is that the budget spent is decreasing so that participants participating in training programs organized by Job Training Institutions are limited because they are adjusted to the budget received. Based on the background described above, the researchers formulated this research problem as follows: 1) how is the implementation of job training programs by PT. JIEC LPK in Blitar Regency; 2) what are the inhibiting factors in the implementation of job training programs in Blitar Regency.

Management According to Sandang P. Siagian, management is expressed as the ability or skill to achieve goals through the activities of other people. Meanwhile, according to Ricky W. Griffin (2014), according to Primary management is the process of planning, organizing, coordinating, and controlling resources in order to achieve goals and objectives effectively and efficiently (Primary, 2020). According to Wijayanto, planning, directing, coordinating and supervising organizational performance by using existing resources to achieve organizational goals and objectives, which is a science and art that defines Management.

According to Dinda Ardiyanti and Abdul Sadad (2021: 157), management functions consist of:

1. Planning, determining strategies and objectives to achieve them, and developing plans to integrate and coordinate activities, all of which are part of this function.
2. Organizing, the function of this management includes setting and preparing work to achieve a goal.
3. Leadership, this function requires collaboration with or through other people to achieve organizational goals.
4. Controlling, this function includes monitoring, comparing, and improving work performance.

According to Sidartha & Bob after goals and strategies have been determined, tasks and structural arrangements have been defined, and people have been hired, trained, and motivated, a situation assessment must be carried out to find out if it is according to plan.

According to Sihotang Human Resource Management Human Resource Management includes the complete process of planning, organizing, directing, and supervising the selection, training, placement, and release of human resources to meet the needs of individuals, communities, government customers, and organizations. According to Veithzal Rvai (2009: 1), HR Management is a branch of general management which includes features of planning, organizing, implementing, and monitoring this process in the functions/fields of production, marketing, finance, and staffing. Human Resource Management (HRM) is the management of people utilization, as well as a set of strategies, processes and activities aimed at helping organizations achieve their goals by combining organizational and individual demands.

The conclusion that can be drawn from some of the theories above is that HR Management is a series of actions in recruiting, developing, and maintaining a workforce that is carried out using management activities, including planning, organizing, activating, and controlling. While HRM functions consist of:

1) *Procurement of Human Resources*: Is an HR management activity that requires the placement of workers needed to help the company achieve its goals. Job analysis, planning, recruitment, and selection and placement of Human Resources.

2) *Development of Human Resources*: The process of providing education and training to new or existing employees to enhance their knowledge and skills. Career planning (Career Planning), career development (Career Growth), organizational development and management, and performance appraisal are steps in the development and training of Human Resources.

3) *Provision of Compensation*: Compensation is Employees or employees are rewarded for the services they have provided to companies or organizations.

4) *Integration*: Integration means matching employee aspirations with organizational needs, therefore considering the feelings and attitudes of employees in determining organizational rules. Workplace motivation, job satisfaction, and leadership are all factors to consider.

5) *Maintenance of Human Resources*: This function means that employees stay in the organization as members with high levels of loyalty and loyalty. The task of maintaining human resources is related to communication in the workplace and occupational health and safety.

According to Setyobudi (2014.P.31) defines that: "training is a systematic process for developing the knowledge, skills and attitudes needed in carrying out one's duties and is expected to be able to influence work performance like the person concerned and the organization where they work". The definition of training according to Pribadi (2014.P.2) that: "training is basically meaningful as an effort made to acquire knowledge, skills and attitudes that can be used immediately to improve performance". Meanwhile, Najib (2015.P.28) argues that "practice means lessons to get used to or acquire certain skills".

The following are the aims and objectives of the training according to Hamalik (2007.P.16):

1. To train, foster and educate workers who have productive skills in the context of implementing organizational programs in the field.
2. Fostering elements of employment who have the desire to continue learning in order to improve themselves as tough, independent and professional workers.
3. Train the workforce according to their talents, interests, values and experience.

According to Pribadi (2014.Pp.9-10), a training program can be said to be effective if it is able to make students or participants master the knowledge, skills and attitudes needed after completing the training program, there is an increase in the participants' learning motivation to want to explore the content or training material, there is an increase in the participants' memory or retention of the content or material that has been trained and provides a great possibility for participants to be able to apply the content or material that has been trained.

In the explanation of article 26 paragraph 5 of Law Number 20 of 2003 it is explained that: "Courses and training are a form of continuing education to develop students' abilities with an emphasis on mastery of skills, competency standards, development of entrepreneurial attitudes and development of professional personality." The conclusion is that community empowerment is giving power to the weak or the powerless to become empowered, be it individuals or communities so that they are able to determine their future and be

able to compete, increase knowledge, skills and even be able to apply what they learn, they can find problems they face and can solve those problems.

Program Implementation Implementation is an effort to realize the strategy by moving people to want to work independently and fully with awareness together to achieve organizational goals effectively and efficiently. The focus of attention on implementation is to understand what happens after a program is declared effective and implementation also involves issues of conflict, decisions and who gets what from a policy. According to Van Horn, implementation or implementation is an action carried out by individuals/officials or government or private groups with the aim of achieving the goals set in the policy. The program is a kind of clear and concrete plan because it consists of predetermined goals, policies, procedures, budgets, and implementation time. The program can also be said to be something that is used to determine which part must be completed first so that it can be used as a guide for implementers. Based on some of the definitions above, it can be said that program implementation is a series of actions carried out by individuals or organizations in the form of carrying out activities, which are supported by policies, procedures and resources, and are designed to produce results to meet the stated goals.

Based on the results of observations made by the author, the instructor experienced problems in delivering the material because there were no modules that were in accordance with the latest SKKNI, while the training programs that were opened were required to refer to the latest SKKNI, namely the 2015 SKKNI. The available modules were still old products and used the 2010 SKKNI and the material is not yet relevant to the user company, so there is input from the company to improve the training program held at BLK, especially the training material, it is hoped that it will be in accordance with industry needs. For this reason, a strategy is urgently needed to improve the quality of training outcomes at vocational training centers, one of which is by developing training modules whose material is adapted to the needs of the labor market.

LITERATURE REVIEW

As a direct consequence of the ongoing process of regional autonomy, there has been healthy competition between these regions to develop their respective regions by mobilizing human resources in these regions. Thus there are higher regional and national job market opportunities, because the need for a reliable and ready-to-use workforce has become a basic need for a region so that the region can develop. Thus, the implementation of tourism development policies cannot only rely on 4 (four) main indicators as stated by Edward, namely communication, bureaucracy, disposition and institutions.

METHODOLOGY

The research conducted in investigating the Implementation of the Occupational Education Program at PT.LPK Jamiatul Indonesia Edutech Certification in Blitar Regency uses a type of research, namely qualitative research which is descriptive analysis in nature. Qualitative research is a social science research approach that collects and analyzes data in the form of words (oral and written) and human activities. Qualitative research is useful for uncovering details of events in order to understand the dynamics of a social reality. The reason for using qualitative methods is so that researchers can get to know the facts more deeply and see the process of implementing the Occupational Education Program at PT.LPK Jamiatul Indonesia Edutech Certification Blitar Regency through data collection qualitative research methods. The first stage, heuristics (data collection) in this stage the author collects sources related to the research material under study, both in the form of primary and secondary sources.

The author conducted research located in Ponggok Village, Ponggok District, Blitar Regency. The following are informants in this study:

1. Head of Planning and Finance Subdivision.
2. Head of Work Placement and Expansion.
3. Head of Training and Workforce Productivity Section.
4. Target group, namely job training participants who are a source of informants who see and assess the implementation of job training by PT.LPK Jamiatul Indonesia Edutech Certification Blitar Regency.

In this research, informants were selected based on the research object and the relationship between the informant and the research is called purposive sampling. In qualitative research, data analysis is an ongoing activity that takes place throughout the research process, from data collection to report writing. (Afrizal, 2017). According to Miles and Huberman (1992) in Afrizal's book, data analysis in qualitative research consists of data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion/verification.

RESULT

PT LPK JAMIATUL INDONESIA EDUTECH CERTIFICATION Office
Address : Ponggok DSN, Ponggok Village/Kelurahan, Kec. Ponggok, Kab. Blitar, East Java Province, Postal Code: 66153. NUMBER : AHU-047325.AH.01.30.Tahun 2023. Business Identification Number (NIB) : 0807230084891. Business Activities: 62023 - Activities for Provision of Electronic Certificates and Services Using Electronic Certificates 69201 - Accounting, Bookkeeping and Examination Activities 69202 - Tax Consulting Activities 70209 - Other Management Consulting Activities 71101 - Architectural Activities 71102 - Engineering Activities and YBDI Technical Consultation 71201 - Certification Services 74311 - Party Professional Certification Activities 1 78101 - Domestic Workers Selection and Placement Activities 78102 - Overseas Workforce Selection and Placement Activities 78104 - Online Workforce Placement Activities (Job Portal) 78200 - Specific Time Manpower Provision Activities 78300 - Human Resource Provision and Human Resource Function Management 78425 - Private Business and Management Job Training 82190 - Photocopying activities, document

preparation and other special office support activities 85452 - Non-formal Islamic religious education 85495 - Private tutoring and counseling education 86902 - Traditional health service activities.

Figure 1. Logo PT.LPK Jamiatul Indonesia Edutech Certification

PT.LPK Jamiatul Indonesia Edutech Certification Blitar Regency has a role in reducing unemployment throughout Indonesia through the field of job placement and expansion which is the government's task, namely by providing job training and workforce placement based on the knowledge possessed by job seekers. therefore the efforts made by PT.LPK Jamiatul Indonesia Edutech Certification Blitar Regency is to provide Job Training Programs. The job training program is in the form of entrepreneurship training and training based on local competencies. In this research, the researcher uses the theory expressed by Edward III, the reason this researcher uses this theory is that there is an interrelated relationship between each indicator in achieving the goals and objectives of the job training program.

Those indicators variables are communication, resources, attitude and bureaucratic structure. Communication Communication indicators play a very important role for job training program implementers in Blitar Regency and all regions in Indonesia. Communication here means how the program can be communicated to the target group and the organization, whether the communication is communicated clearly and consistently. The importance of communication in the implementation of a job training program is for the implementation of the program to run effectively, this is so important because the greater the understanding of the target group about the program to be implemented, the less likely it is for rejection and errors in applying the program. Understanding that PT.LPK Jamiatul Indonesia Edutech Certification Blitar Regency has carried out good coordination within its organizational environment, namely between the heads of services, to the field of work placement and expansion as well as the heads of the training and work productivity sections, good relations and communication are established. Meanwhile, socialization is carried out through the Musrenbang in each sub-district.

PT.LPK Jamiatul Indonesia Edutech Certification Blitar Regency does not directly disseminate work course programs to the target group. according to the researchers, the dissemination carried out was not comprehensive because it was only known by the community who would become participants who had been determined by the sub-district only. It can be concluded here that there is still a lack of dissemination of work course programs to the community as the target group. Regarding the clarity of the information provided, it is known from the

responses that the researchers asked them that they thought that the information provided was categorized as sufficient, meaning that the information provided was not very clear. Therefore, a balance of communication between program implementers and target groups must be achieved. and the importance of efficient communication so that the target group understands the aims and objectives of the work course program PT.LPK Jamiatul Indonesia Edutech Certification Blitar Regency. Resources Even though the program content has been given clearly and consistently, if the executor lacks the resources to implement it, the program implementation will not run effectively.

Resources according to Edward III consist of Human Resources and Financial Resources which consist of employees of the right size with the necessary expertise or competence, important and sufficient information to implement policies/programs, as well as the fulfillment of related resources in program implementation, the availability of authority to ensure that this program can be implemented as expected, and the availability of supporting facilities that can be used to carry out program activities, such as funds and infrastructure including buildings, equipment, land, and other supplies. The source of funds for organizing this job training comes from LPK Private Funds and Job Training Registration Fees. From this fund, participants receive stationery, training materials, consumption, transportation, certificates and capital to start their own business. For human resources, the results that researchers have obtained are that the level of understanding of employees or employees is quite good, but in the implementation of this program, special staffing is needed for training instructors because in the implementation of this job training program, experts are still used from outside, namely private job training institutions that in Indonesia. However, the instructor for the implementation of job training in Blitar Regency already has instructor certification and is competent. Financial resources, such as funds, are still limited, limiting training participants, as well as facilities, namely the absence of BLK in Blitar Regency, so they have to rely on BLK in East Java Province because the training equipment available in BLK in East Java Province is very complete. This makes the implementation of job training programs less than optimal.

Disposition Disposition is the third sign in the approach to the implementation of job training programs in Blitar District. This disposition is the nature and characteristics possessed by an executor. Implementation of job training programs will be effective, if program implementers not only know what to do but also have the desire to carry out the program. If the executor has a good attitude, then he can run the program well in accordance with the goals and objectives that have been set previously. Therefore, a good executor must have characters such as honesty, commitment, and democracy.

Executors with a high level of dedication and integrity will always succeed in passing the program's challenges. This candor can direct executors to remain within the scope of the program as described in the predetermined criteria. The implementation of this job training program has good integrity and commitment. This good disposition can move the program well according to what policy makers want. With an attitude of integrity that exists in executors, there is no

misappropriation, such as in funding. All activities carried out, the executor is very responsible for the program he is implementing. Another thing was also seen from the responses of the training participants who stated that the implementers provided guidance and provided good service to the training participants. Resources Even if the resources in implementing a program are sufficient, and the implementers are aware of what is being done and want to do it, program implementation will be poor if the bureaucratic structure is inadequate. In addition to communication indicators, resources and attitudes of implementers, the bureaucratic structure is also very influential in program implementation. The bureaucratic structure in this case involves two key elements, namely the mechanism aspect and the implementing organizational structure aspect.

The procedure for implementing this program has generally been determined through Standard Operating Procedures (SPO). Standard operating procedures (SPO) are a set of rules that must be followed by each party. Because it will be a guide in implementation. A good SOP follows a clear, logical, and simple framework that is easy for everyone to understand. The second aspect is organizational structure , an organizational structure that is too complex will tend to weaken supervision and cause excessive bureaucracy, which results in organizational activities becoming less flexible. Therefore the organizational structure must be designed concisely and flexibly. The bureaucratic structure indicators analyzed through the SPO and division of tasks at the Blitar District Manpower Office are well regulated. This is indicated by the existence of responsibilities and a clear division of tasks among the elements of the existing organization. Judging from the organizational structure of the Blitar District Manpower Office, based on Blitar District Head Regulation Number 63 of 2016 concerning Position, Organizational Structure, Duties and Functions and Work Procedures of the Blitar District Manpower Office. The organizational structure of the Blitar Regency Manpower Office which manages the Job Training Program is the Head of Service, the Job Placement and Expansion Division, and the Workforce Training and Productivity Section. this will create an efficient organizational structure, so that the bureaucracy becomes simpler and easier and program implementation becomes effective.

Assessment is also carried out by the management in order to carry out repairs/maintenance of the programs that have been carried out through meeting activities with staff at LPK JIEC once a month. The material designed by the tutor is in accordance with its implementation in learning so that the achievement of the material can be in accordance with the expected target. The results obtained by students while participating in the training at LPK JIEC are also satisfied because they gain knowledge about language, discipline, and work skills. This is in accordance with the statement of Ridwan and Suryono (2015: 231) which explains that program assessment can show student satisfaction with the learning program, follow-up in the form of implementation of the learning given to students, the impact that arises on students and institutions, as well as the benefits that are obtained.

DISCUSSION

The following are several types of job training management planning at PT LPK Jamiatul Indonesia Edutech Certification:

1. *Analysis of Training Needs*: This stage involves identifying training needs based on performance evaluations, organizational needs, and expectations of the trainees.
2. *Planning Training Goals and Objectives*: This stage involves setting clear goals and objectives for the training, which must match the identified needs.
3. *Determination of Training Methods and Materials*: This stage involves selecting appropriate learning methods, such as face-to-face training, online training, or simulation-based training. In addition, the training materials must also be selected and arranged properly.
4. *Planning the Training Schedule and Duration*: This stage involves determining the training schedule according to the availability of participants and the operational needs of the organization. The duration of the training must also be considered so that participants have sufficient time to master the material.
5. *Selection of Trainees*: This stage involves the process of selecting trainees based on predetermined criteria, such as job level, job requirements, or development potential.
6. *Training Budget Planning*: This stage involves calculating the costs needed to carry out the training, including costs for facilities, instructors, materials, and other supporting equipment.
7. *Training Evaluation and Monitoring*: This stage involves training monitoring and evaluation, both during the training and after the training is over. This evaluation aims to evaluate the effectiveness of the training and identify areas for future improvement.
8. *Preparation of Training Reports*: This stage involves compiling reports on the results of the training, including participant evaluations, success in achieving objectives, and suggestions for future improvement.

The following are several types of job training management implementation at PT LPK Jamiatul Indonesia Edutech Certification:

1. *On-The-Job Training (OTJ)*: This training is conducted while employees are working at the workplace on a daily basis. Employees are provided with direct guidance and guidance by supervisors or mentors as they perform their daily tasks. This training helps employees to learn and develop practical skills relevant to their jobs.
2. *Off-The-Job Training*: This training takes place in a different location than the normal workplace, such as a training center or training institute. This training can include lectures, workshops, role-plays, computer simulations and practical exercises. It helps employees to gain broader theoretical understanding and practical skills.
3. *Simulation Training*: Simulation training involves the use of computer software or role-playing games that allow employees to experience situations they might face in a real job. It helps employees to develop problem solving, decision making and time management skills.

4. *Structured Training*: This training involves the use of pre-prepared instructional materials. This training often involves the use of presentations, textbooks, or online learning materials. The purpose of structured training is to provide the necessary basic knowledge for employees to carry out their duties properly.

5. *Self-Training*: This training gives employees complete control over their own learning process. Employees can use online resources, books or other learning materials to develop their skills. Self-training allows employees to learn at their own pace and learning style.

6. *Reciprocal Training*: Reciprocal training involves feedback provided by superiors, co-workers or coaches to employees. The purpose of this training is to help employees understand their strengths, identify areas that need improvement, and implement the necessary corrective actions.

7. *Specific Skills Training*: This training aims to develop technical skills or specific skills needed in a particular job. Examples of specific skills training include training in the use of specific software, specific tools, or specific operational techniques. Options for implementing job training may vary depending on the organizational setting, the type of work, and the goals to be achieved.

The following are several types of job training management evaluation at PT LPK Jamiatul Indonesia Edutech Certification:

1. *Reaction Evaluation*: This evaluation is carried out by seeking feedback from the training participants regarding their satisfaction with the training. Participants may be asked to fill out a questionnaire or answer questions related to their experiences during the training. The purpose of this evaluation is to find out what the participants think about the quality of the training, instructors, and training materials.

2. *Learning Evaluation*: This evaluation aims to measure the level of understanding and increased knowledge of the participants after attending the training. This can be done by means of written tests, examinations, or special assignments that test understanding of the training material. Learning evaluation assists in assessing the effectiveness of the training in acquiring and increasing participants' knowledge.

3. *Behavioral Evaluation*: This evaluation involves observing the behavior of the participants after they have attended the training. This can be done through direct observation by superiors or coaches, performance appraisals, or interviews. Behavioral evaluation aims to assess whether participants apply the skills and knowledge acquired during the training in their work context.

4. *Impact Evaluation*: This evaluation is conducted to assess the effect of the training on individual or work group performance. This can involve measuring employee performance before and after training, sales data, customer satisfaction, or other relevant performance metrics. Impact evaluation helps in determining whether the training has been successful in increasing the performance and achievement of organizational goals.

5. *Evaluation of ROI (Return on Investment)*: This evaluation is a method to measure the financial benefits received from investment in job training. This involves comparing the costs incurred for training with the resulting financial benefits, such as increased productivity, higher sales, or reduced costs of damage or errors. ROI evaluation helps in understanding the value of training in terms of the business

benefits that can be obtained. Each type of evaluation has its own merits in evaluating the effectiveness of job training. The combination of several types of evaluation can provide more comprehensive insight into the success of the training program.

Obstacles in improving the quality of job training educational institutions at PT LPK Jamiatul Indonesia Edutech Certification include:

1. *Lack of Resources*: Vocational training educational institutions may experience constraints in accessing sufficient resources, such as limited budgets, lack of adequate facilities and equipment, or shortage of qualified teaching staff.
2. *Curriculum Irrelevance to market needs*: If the curriculum taught at job training educational institutions does not match the needs and demands of the labor market, it will be difficult for trainees to find suitable jobs after completing the training.
3. *Insufficient Quality of Teaching Staff*: If teaching staff in training educational institutions are of less quality, then teaching and learning will not be effective. This will have a negative impact on the quality of the training provided.

Efforts that can be made to improve the quality of job training educational institutions are:

1. *Increased Resources*: More budget and investment should be allocated to vocational training educational institutions to be able to access adequate resources, including necessary facilities and equipment.
2. *Increasing the Relevance of the Curriculum*: The curriculum should be updated regularly to ensure that the material being taught is in accordance with the needs and demands of the current job market. There needs to be good communication between job training educational institutions, industry, and companies to understand current and future workforce needs.
3. *Development of Teaching Staff*: Vocational training educational institutions should carry out continuous training and development of teaching staff to improve teaching quality. Teachers also need to have knowledge and skills relevant to the industry and job market they teach.
4. *Cooperation With Industry*: Closer cooperation between job training educational institutions and industry can assist in the development of relevant curricula, provide apprenticeship or practical work opportunities for trainees, and ensure that training is held in accordance with the workforce requirements desired by industry.
5. *Evaluation and Monitoring*: Vocational training educational institutions need to carry out regular evaluations of the training programs held and monitor the success of the participants after completing the training. This will help to identify weaknesses and correct deficiencies in an effort to improve the quality of training. Professional job training is a process of formal or informal education designed to increase one's knowledge, skills and abilities in the world of work. Professional job training is characterized by a systematic and structured approach, using effective methods and techniques, and carried out by qualified teaching staff or instructors.

In conclusion, professional job training has several important characteristics, including:

1. *Clear Objectives*: Professional on the job training should have clear and specific objectives, so that participants understand what they need to achieve after completing the training.
2. *Relevant Curriculum*: Professional job training must have a curriculum that is relevant to the needs and demands of the labor market. The curriculum should keep up with the latest developments in the industry and prepare participants with the skills required for the desired job.
3. *Effective Methods and Techniques*: Professional on the job training uses effective methods and techniques to provide optimal learning. This method can involve a combination of theory sessions, simulations, practical exercises, and ongoing monitoring and feedback.
4. *Qualified Teaching Staff*: Teachers or instructors teaching in professional on-the-job training must have knowledge and experience relevant to the field of training. They must also have good teaching skills to facilitate the participants' learning process.
5. *Evaluation and Monitoring*: Professional on the job training should involve a structured evaluation and monitoring system to measure the success of the participants after completing the training. This is important to ensure that the objectives of the training have been achieved and that participants have the skills needed in the world of work. Taking these characteristics into account, professional job training can provide significant benefits to participants, including increased job opportunities, increased productivity, and career advancement.

CONCLUSION

Based on the exposure in the discussion described above, it can be concluded that:

1. The implementation of the job training program at PT.LPK Jamiatul Indonesia Edutech Certification, Blitar Regency, still has weaknesses or is still not optimal in its implementation according to the program implementation signs conveyed by Edward III, among which are still not suitable, namely communication and resources. Communication is related to the low socialization of job training programs to the community as the target group. The reason was that the socialization that was carried out was not comprehensive because those who only knew about the activities of the job training program were only the community who would become participants who had been determined by the sub-district only. Then from the clarity of the information, the information provided was not very clear so that the target group did not know well the goals and objectives in implementing the job training program run by PT.LPK Jamiatul Indonesia Edutech Certification, Blitar Regency. Then the resource indicators relate to human resources and financial resources. The understanding of staff or apparatus is good enough, but for training instructors in implementing this job training program they still use external experts, namely Private Job Training Institutions in Pangkalan Blitar. For financial resources such as funds which are still limited so as to make training participants limited, as well as facilities, namely the absence of

BLK and workshops. While the indicators that have been achieved are the disposition and structure of the bureaucracy. Disposition is related to honesty, good commitment possessed by program implementers. For indicators of bureaucratic structure related to SOPs and organizational structure, SOPs and division of tasks at LPK Blitar Regency have been well regulated, it can be seen from the existence of a clear division of tasks and responsibilities among existing members of the organization.

2. The factors that hinder the implementation of job training programs at PT.LPK Jamiatul Indonesia Edutech Certification Blitar Regency are:

- 1) shortage of training teaching staff.
- 2) there is still no Job Training Center, to carry out job training programs such as workshop training, a Training Center is needed Work and Workshop.
- 3) budget constraints.
- 4) training participants are not on target.

In conclusion, professional job training has several important characteristics, including:

1. Clear objectives.
2. Relevant curriculum.
3. Effective methods and techniques.
4. Qualified teaching staff.
5. Evaluation and monitoring.

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